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DEFINITION OF CLASS1-4 METRICS FOR THE ARCTIC

MERSEA DELIVERABLE D5.4.5

by

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Acronyms

ARGO	global array of profiling floats
GMES	Marine EnviRonment and Security for the European Area
NAT	North Atlantic region
NEA	North East Atlantic region (and forecasting TEP)
SST	Sea Surface Temperature
TBD	To Be Defined
TEP	Thematic Portal
ULS	Upward Looking Sonar
WIN	Wide Integrated Network
WP	Work Package

Applicable and Reference documents

- [REF1] Overall Specification of the MERSEA Integrated System WP5.1., 24 March 2005“. MERSEA-WP05-MERCA-STR-0005.01A”
- [REF2] Guidelines for data provider - Mersea Gridded Data Product Format. MERSEA-WP06-CLS-UMAN-001. 01/07/2005.
- [REF3] [MERSEA Strand intercomparison document](#)
http://mersea.nersc.no/~mersea/Public/D4.1_Metrics_NAT_MED_v5.pdf
- [REF4] List of internal Metrics, specification for implementation. WP 5. Authors: L Crosnier, F. Hernandez et al. 24 March 2005.
MERSEA-WP05-MERCA-STR0007_01A.doc
- [REF5] Minutes of the WP09-WP10 “Class 4 meeting” Exeter, Feb 2005.
MERSEA-WP05-NERSC-MIN-001.CLASS4.doc
- [REF6] Meeting report. TOP 1 meeting. Issy les Moulineaux. May 24-25, 2005. P. Bahurel, M. Bell, Y. Desaubies. 31 May 2005.
MERSEA-WP01-IFR-ECMR-006-01.doc
- [REF7] Summary of WP9 Meeting, Exeter, 1-3 February 2006. Mike Bell (NCOF/UKMO)
- [REF8] Assessment during TOP1: guideline for metrics implementation. 6 Feb. 2006
MERSEA-WP5-MERCA-STR-0014-01B
- [REF9] List of internal metrics for the MERSEA-GODAE Global Ocean: Specification for implementation. L. Crosnier et al.. 14 March 2006.
MERSEA-WP05-MERCA-STR0015.01A.doc.
- [REF10] Guideline for the GODAE providers: Convention for the GODAE files, OpenDap and Live Access Server. L. Crosnier. 14 March 2006.
MERSEA-WP05-MERCA-STR0016.01A.doc.
- [REF11] Description of MERSEA Core System version v.1. Project Deliverables D9.3.2. 6 April 2006. M. J. Bell. MERSEA-WP09-METUK-STR004.01A.doc.
- [REF12] Executive Committee Meeting Report: MEC-5. Paris, December 8-9, 2005. January 25, 2006. Y. Desaubies. MERSEA-WP01-IFR-ECMR-009.1c.doc.
- [REF13] MERSEA Services specification for Version 1 of MERSEA System
WP5, January 2006
MERSEA-WP05-MERCA-STR-0010.01A
- [REF14] First Version of the MERSEA WWW Ocean Forecasting Portal. MERSEA-WP06-CLS-TECN-002. 3 May 2005.
- [REF15] Guidelines for Data Provider- Quick Opendap Installation & Configuration Guide. MERSEA-WP06-CLS-UMAN-002. 30/09/2005.
- [REF16] Guidelines to Mersea Partners to contribute to the Mersea System. MERSEA-WP06-IFR-UMAN-001. 01/01/2006.

- [REF17] In-situ real-time data quality control.
MERSEA-WP03-IFR-UMAN-001-01B.doc. 04/2005
- [REF18] Guideline to In-Situ TEP User. D3.6.1
MERSEA-WP03-IFR-UMAN-002-01A.doc. 12/01/2006

Introduction

1. Context

In the framework of the WP5 –MERSEA IP system design, see [REF1], the validation procedures are defined in the task 5.4. For the first Target Operational Phase (TOP1), a validation exercise was requested during the workshop on “TOP1 and MERSEA V1 definition”, held in Paris on 24-25 May 2005 [REF6]. Then, it was decided during MEC-5 [REF12] a limited and delayed mode validation exercise for TOP1. This plan has been discussed during the WP5-6-9 meeting, held in Exeter on 1-3 February, 2006 [REF7].

The TOP1 assessment objective is to provide a first validation of the MERSEA system V1, as defined by [REF11]. The TOP1 validation plan and a metrics implementation guide has been written [REF8], summing up the discussions mentioned above that occurred for the past 12 months. According to these rules, from MERSEA Strand1 heritage [REF3], metrics definitions have been up-graded for the Arctic region in this document that details particularly the sea-ice metrics. Ocean metrics in the Arctic are detailed together with other ocean regions in the global ocean document [REF9]. A companion document is providing a technical guidance for implementing the metrics at the forecasting TEP level [10].

These metrics documents correspond to the WP5 deliverables D5.4.5 “List of internal metrics for the MERSEA/GODAE Global Ocean, and specification for implementation”.

2. Purpose of the document

This document is an extension of the conventions used for class 1-4 files in MERSEA Strand1 [REF3]. It takes into account the Class 1-3 definition [REF4], and consideration from Class 4 discussions and workshops [REF5]. This document aims to describe more specifically the sea-ice metrics. Ocean metrics are detailed in the global ocean document [REF9]. Metrics types are:

- Class1: Standard model products 2D and 3D interpolated fields on a regular polar stereographic grid
- Class2: Other model products 2D fields along sections, 1D tables at point locations.
- Class3: derived quantities computed on a daily basis.
- Class4: derived quantities to assess model performance, computed on a weekly basis

The document describes the metrics to be used for Arctic forecast products and should be used by people willing to contribute to and access the Arctic TEP, which is organized following the data management specified in MERSEA –for more details, see [REF2, REF14, REF15, and REF16]

The goal is to assess the present forecasting systems. According to Le Provost et al (2002, see REF8 for the full reference), three criteria family have been identified:

- **Consistency**: verifying that the system outputs are consistent with the current knowledge of the ocean circulation and climatologies
- **Quality**: quantifying the differences between the system best results (analysis) and the sea truth, as estimated from observations, preferably using independent observations (not assimilated).
- **Performance** (or **accuracy**): quantifying the short term forecast capacity of each system, i.e. Answering the questions do we perform better than persistency? better than climatology?

Class 1 data

The class 1 files produced in MERSEA Strand 1 contained 2D and 3D fields with regular longitude-latitude coordinates, and at predefined depth levels. The file format in MERSEA-S1 was NetCDF, following the [CF-1.0](#) NetCDF conventions.

This section is an extension of the netcdf variables and conventions used for so-called class 1 files in MERSEA Strand 1, see the [MERSEA Strand 1 document](#). The class 1 files produced in MERSEA Strand 1 contained 2D and 3D fields with regular longitude-latitude coordinates, and at predefined depth levels. The file format in MERSEA-S1 was NetCDF, following the [CF-1.0](#) NetCDF conventions.

Defining class files for the Arctic require that we should reconsider the standard output grid to be used, and the variables that should be included in the NetCDF files. We still follow the [CF-1.0](#) NetCDF conventions.

3. Horizontal projection

In MERSEA Strand 1 [REF4], all model fields were interpolated onto a longitude-latitude grid, in order to compare the different model fields more easily. A common grid should be used for the Arctic portal of MERSEA IP as well, but a longitude-latitude grid becomes awkward for the Arctic. It is therefore suggested that we do the comparison on a polar stereographic grid. The formulas are as described by Snyder(1987), going from projection x,y coordinates to longitude,latitude using the following formulas:

$$\begin{aligned}\rho &= \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \\ c &= \arctan(2\rho / r) \\ \lambda &= \arccos(\cos(c)) \frac{180}{\pi} \\ \theta &= \arctan(x \sin(c), -y \sin(c)) \frac{180}{\pi} - 45\end{aligned}$$

Where x,y are the projection coordinates, and θ, λ are longitude,latitude in degrees. The variable r is the radius of the earth, here set to $r=6378.273$ km. This formula assumes that the earth is a perfect sphere. The **units of x and y** are in **kilometers on the polar tangent plane** (this is a potentially misleading unit that slightly overestimates the real curvilinear distances, it is only exact at the North Pole). The following shows the area within x-coordinate -3800 to 3800 and y-coordinate -5500 to 5500.

Figure 1: Arctic standard projection grid.

4. Horizontal resolution

Following the 1/8th (~12.5 km) degree grid used in MERSEA Strand 1, the following setup of the coordinate variables is suggested:

X: ranging from -3800 km to 3800 km, with a step of 12.5 km
Y: ranging from -5500 km to 5500 km, with a step of 12.5 km

Table 1: Class 1 coordinates and ranges

The true resolution is exactly 12.5 km at the North Pole and is slightly higher in the rest of the region. These x,y variables are the coordinate axes of the netcdf file. The coordinate ranges cover the Arctic regions, including the Bering and Okhotsk Sea.

An implementation detail has proven to be quite useful with these x,y-coordinates when they are put in the netcdf file. If we let one x-,y-unit be 100 km, it becomes much easier to handle the datafiles within the framework of the Live Access Server (which will be used to produce illustrations online). This is because the LAS-tools are designed for presenting data having longitude-/latitude-coordinates. Using units of 100-km makes it easier to shortcut the LAS in-built limitations (because x and y then fit within the [-180,180] and [-90,90] ranges).

Using these projections and units, we get the output (Table 2) for describing the grid in a NetCDF file. x,y are the projection coordinates, defined above. The *standard_names* of x and y used here are [CF-1.0](#)-compliant when longitude and latitude axis are not used as coordinate axes in the NetCDF files. The variable "*polar stereographic*" is not strictly necessary, but [CF-1.0](#) conventions suggest it should be included. It is an empty variable, with some information on the polar stereographic projection contained in its attributes. Each variable will point to this variable through a variable attribute (see the section 0 on variables). Finally, the longitude and latitude of the x/y-grid should be included as well.

The CF-1.0 convention is described here:

<http://www.cgd.ucar.edu/cms/eaton/cf-metadata/CF-1.0.html>

```

dimensions:
  x = 609 ;
  y = 881 ;
float x(x) ;
  x:axis = "X" ;
  x:standard_name = "projection_x_coordinate" ;
  x:units = "100 km" ;
float y(y) ;
  y:standard_name = "projection_y_coordinate" ;
  y:axis = "Y" ;
  y:units = "100 km" ;
int polar_stereographic ;
  polar_stereographic:grid_mapping_name =
"polar_stereographic" ;
  polar_stereographic:latitude_of_projection_origin = 90.f ;
  polar_stereographic:longitude_of_projection_origin = 45.f
;
  polar_stereographic:scale_factor_at_projection_origin =
1.f ;
  polar_stereographic:false_easting = 0.f ;
  polar_stereographic:false_northing = 0.f ;
float longitude(y, x) ;
  longitude:units = "degrees" ;
  longitude:valid_range = -180.f, 180.f ;
  longitude:long_name = "longitude" ;
  longitude:missing_value = -1.e+14f ;
float latitude(y, x) ;
  latitude:units = "degrees" ;
  latitude:valid_range = -90.f, 90.f ;
  latitude:standard_name = "latitude" ;
  latitude:long_name = "latitude" ;
  latitude:missing_value = -1.e+14f ;

```

Table 2: Class 1 grid definition as listed in the NetCDF files.

5. Vertical grid

The vertical depth levels are chosen the same than in MERSEA Strand 1 North Atlantic Class 1 [REF4].

ARCTIC	0	30	50	100	200	400	700	1000	1500	2000	2500	3000
--------	---	----	----	-----	-----	-----	-----	------	------	------	------	------

Table 3: Arctic Class1 Standard vertical levels (in meters).

And the corresponding listing of the vertical grid variable in the NetCDF file is illustrated by Table 4:

```
float depth(depth) ;
    depth:long_name = "depth" ;
    depth:units = "m" ;
    depth:standard_name = "depth" ;
    depth:positive = "down" ;
    depth:axis = "Z" ;
```

Table 4: Class 1 vertical grid definition as listed in the NetCDF files.

6. Variables

Table 6 shows the variables suggested for the Class 1 files, also included are units to use (units attribute in NetCDF file), along with the standard name attribute of the NetCDF file. Please note that **all variables are grid cell averages**. This means that for an ice floe of thickness h covering a fractional area c in a grid cell, the grid cell average ice thickness becomes $c \cdot h$. The same applies to all ice variables, occasionally against all common sense, for instance for snow thickness and ice drift. This follows however strictly the [CF-1.0](#) conventions (although it could be confusing to the end user!). Dividing by the ice concentration c can retrieve the quantities relative to the ice fraction.

One exception to the CF convention has been made for vector variables for the following reason: it is misleading to look at Northward velocities on a polar projection. In order to improve user-friendliness, **velocity vectors are rotated onto the polar projection**. They will be x and y velocities instead of Eastward and Northward.

Note: After request from NERSC to the CF mailing list, a positive response indicates that the above vector rotation will be included in the next release of the CF convention.

The “ q_{tot} ” variable is the **heat flux going into the ocean**. The “ q_{totair} ” variable is the atmospheric heat flux on the ice/ocean surface from the atmosphere (again, a grid cell average). These two variables differ if new ice melts/freezes, and if the heat stored in the ice changes. The “ q_{sw} ” variable is the shortwave heat flux on the ice/ocean surface while “ $albedo$ ” is the grid cell average surface albedo.

Additional attributes should be included for each NetCDF variable as well, in addition to the units and *standard_name* attributes. Table 5 is an example for the *temperature* variable:

```
short temperature(depth, y, x) ;
    temperature:long_name = "Potential temperature of sea water" ;
    temperature:units = "degrees_celsius" ;
    temperature:missing_value = -32767s ;
    temperature:_FillValue = -32767s ;
    temperature:standard_name = "sea_water_potential_temperature" ;
    temperature:add_offset = 21.f ;
    temperature:scale_factor = 0.0007325336f ;
    temperature:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
    temperature:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
    temperature:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
```

Table 5: Class 1 variable definition and attributes as listed in the NetCDF files (here for the temperature).

Each variable has the “*grid_mapping*” attribute, which points to the description of the projection used (see section 0 on horizontal grid). The attribute named “*coordinates*” should be included in the NetCDF file when longitude and latitude are not the coordinate variables of the file. It points to the variables with true longitude and latitude positions of the grid. The “*cell_methods*” attribute indicates that the variable is a mean value for a grid box and over time.

The “*add_offset*” and “*scale_factor*” attributes are not compulsory; they are only needed if one chooses to represent variables as NetCDF type “*short*” (the Artic forecasting system TEP TOPAZ netcdf files do so). The “*_FillValue*” attribute is used to indicate missing data; it should be of the same NetCDF type as the variable.

Variable Name	Standard_name attribute	unit	dimensions
Temperature	sea_water_potential_temperature	Degrees celsius	3D
Salinity	sea_water_salinity	psu	3D
U	X_sea_water_velocity	m s-1	3D
V	Y_sea_water_velocity	m s-1	3D
Bsfd	ocean_barotropic_streamfunction	m ³ s-1	2D
Mlp	ocean_mixed_layer_thickness	m	2D
Taux	surface_downward_x_stress	pascal	2D
Tauy	surface_downward_y_stress	pascal	2D
Qtot	surface_downward_heat_flux_in_sea_water	W m-2	2D
Fwflux	water_flux_into_ocean	kg m-2 s-1	2D
Tauxice	downward_x_stress_at_sea_ice_base	pascal	2D
Tauyice	downward_y_stress_at_sea_ice_base	pascal	2D
Qtotair	surface_downward_heat_flux_in_air	W m-2	2D
Qsw	net_downward_shortwave_flux_in_air	W m-2	2D
Fice	Sea_ice_area_fraction	-	2D
Hice	Sea_ice_thickness	m	2D
Hsnow	surface_snow_thickness	m	2D
Uice	X_sea_ice_velocity	m s-1	2D
Vice	Y_sea_ice_velocity	m s-1	2D
Htndncy	tendency_of_sea_ice_thickness_due_to_thermodynamics	m s-1	2D

Table 6: Suggested Variables to be included, along with standard_name attribute and dimensions. NB: All variables are grid-cell averages.

Note: The Albedo variable has been removed from the list since it is not common to all systems (not used in FOAM, the North East Atlantic forecasting TEP).

7. File name and global attributes

Following MERSEA Strand 1, we use the following file naming convention:

`{model}_{version}_mersea_arctic_grid1to8_class1_b{date}_f{date}9999.nc`
model: system name of the forecasting TEP
version: system version of the forecasting TEP

arctic stands for the Arctic region

grid1to8 stands for the horizontal resolution, here 1/8th degree

The first date is the bulletin date, the last date is forecast (or field) date. 9999 to define (or not) *hhmm*

Table 7: class 1 file name convention see also Table 11

. An example for TOPAZ field produced 30th June 2004 and valid 09th July (T0+9 forecast):

```
topaz_V2_mersea_arctic_grid1to8_da_class1_b20040630_f200407099999.nc
```

For global attribute, we suggest a reference to the MERSEA web site in the “*references*” attribute. We should also have the “*Conventions*” tag set to “*CF-1.0*”. Otherwise it should be up to the providers to set these. Table 8 is an example for a TOPAZ NetCDF file:

```
// global attributes:
:title = "TOPAZ model results" ;
:comment = "Daily Averaged fields" ;
:institution = "NERSC, Thormoehlens gate 47, N-5006 Bergen,
Norway" ;
:history = "20051013:Created by program hyc2proj, version V0.1" ;
:source = "NERSC-HYCOM model fields" ;
:references = "http://topaz.nersc.no http://mersea.eu.org" ;
:field_type = "Daily average fields" ;
:Conventions = "CF-1.0" ;
:field_date = "2004-01-01" ;
:bulletin_date = "2004-01-01" ;
:bulletin_type = "Hindcast" ;
```

Table 8: Class 1 global attributes as listed in the NetCDF files (here for the Arctic TEP TOPAZ forecasting system).

8. Example

Output from `ncdump` from an example file:

```
netcdf N31DAILY_start00000101_dump00000101 {
dimensions:
  x = 609 ;
  y = 881 ;
  depth = 12 ;
variables:
  int polar_stereographic ;
    polar_stereographic:grid_mapping_name="polar_stereographic" ;
    polar_stereographic:latitude_of_projection_origin = 90.f;
    polar_stereographic:longitude_of_projection_origin =45.f;
    polar_stereographic:scale_factor_at_projection_origin=1.;
    polar_stereographic:false_easting = 0.f ;
    polar_stereographic:false_northing = 0.f ;
  float x(x) ;
    x:axis = "X" ;
    x:standard_name = "projection_x_coordinate" ;
    x:units = "100 km" ;
  float longitude(y, x) ;
    longitude:units = "degrees" ;
    longitude:valid_range = -180.f, 180.f ;
    longitude:long_name = "longitude" ;
    longitude:missing_value = -1.e+14f ;
  float y(y) ;
    y:standard_name = "projection_y_coordinate" ;
    y:axis = "Y" ;
    y:units = "100 km" ;
```

```

float latitude(y, x) ;
    latitude:units = "degrees" ;
    latitude:valid_range = -90.f, 90.f ;
    latitude:standard_name = "latitude" ;
    latitude:long_name = "latitude" ;
    latitude:missing_value = -1.e+14f ;
float depth(depth) ;
    depth:long_name = "depth" ;
    depth:units = "m" ;
    depth:valid_range = 0.f, 3001.f ;
    depth:standard_name = "depth" ;
    depth:positive = "down" ;
    depth:axis = "Z" ;
short temperature(depth, y, x) ;
    temperature:long_name = "Potential temperature of sea water" ;
    temperature:units = "degrees_celsius" ;
    temperature:missing_value = -32767s ;
    temperature:_FillValue = -32767s ;
    temperature:standard_name = "sea_water_potential_temperature" ;
    temperature:add_offset = 21.f ;
    temperature:scale_factor = 0.0007325336f ;
    temperature:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
    temperature:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
    temperature:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short salinity(depth, y, x) ;
    salinity:long_name = "Salinity of sea water" ;
    salinity:units = "psu" ;
    salinity:missing_value = -32767s ;
    salinity:_FillValue = -32767s ;
    salinity:standard_name = "sea_water_salinity" ;
    salinity:add_offset = 25.f ;
    salinity:scale_factor = 0.0007630559f ;
    salinity:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
    salinity:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
    salinity:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short u(depth, y, x) ;
    u:long_name = "X velocity component of sea water" ;
    u:units = "m s-1" ;
    u:missing_value = -32767s ;
    u:_FillValue = -32767s ;
    u:standard_name = "x_sea_water_velocity" ;
    u:add_offset = 0.f ;
    u:scale_factor = 0.0003052223f ;
    u:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
    u:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
    u:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short v(depth, y, x) ;
    v:long_name = "Y velocity component of sea water" ;
    v:units = "m s-1" ;
    v:missing_value = -32767s ;
    v:_FillValue = -32767s ;
    v:standard_name = "y_sea_water_velocity" ;
    v:add_offset = 0.f ;
    v:scale_factor = 0.0003052223f ;
    v:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
    v:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
    v:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short bsfd(y, x) ;
    bsfd:long_name = "Barotropic Streamfunction of the ocean" ;
    bsfd:units = "m3 s-1" ;
    bsfd:missing_value = -32767s ;
    bsfd:_FillValue = -32767s ;
    bsfd:standard_name = "ocean_barotropic_streamfunction" ;
    bsfd:add_offset = 0.f ;
    bsfd:scale_factor = 305222.3f ;
    bsfd:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
    bsfd:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
    bsfd:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short mlp(y, x) ;
    mlp:long_name = "Density Defined Mixed Layer Depth" ;
    mlp:units = "m" ;
    mlp:missing_value = -32767s ;
    mlp:_FillValue = -32767s ;

```

```

mlp:standard_name = "ocean_mixed_layer_thickness" ;
mlp:add_offset = 3000.f ;
mlp:scale_factor = 0.0915667f ;
mlp:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
mlp:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
mlp:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short tau(x, y, x) ;
tau:long_name = "Area averaged atmospheric stress – x component" ;
tau:units = "pascal" ;
tau:missing_value = -32767s ;
tau:_FillValue = -32767s ;
tau:standard_name = "surface_downward_x_stress" ;
tau:add_offset = 0.f ;
tau:scale_factor = 6.104447e-05f ;
tau:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
tau:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
tau:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short tau(y, x) ;
tau:long_name = "Area averaged atmospheric stress – y component" ;
tau:units = "pascal" ;
tau:missing_value = -32767s ;
tau:_FillValue = -32767s ;
tau:standard_name = "surface_downward_y_stress" ;
tau:add_offset = 0.f ;
tau:scale_factor = 6.104447e-05f ;
tau:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
tau:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
tau:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short tauice(x, y, x) ;
tauice:long_name = "Area averaged ice stress on ocean – x component" ;
tauice:units = "pascal" ;
tauice:missing_value = -32767s ;
tauice:_FillValue = -32767s ;
tauice:standard_name = "downward_x_stress_at_sea_ice_base" ;
tauice:add_offset = 0.f ;
tauice:scale_factor = 6.104447e-05f ;
tauice:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
tauice:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
tauice:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short tauice(y, x) ;
tauice:long_name = "Area averaged ice stress on ocean – y component" ;
tauice:units = "pascal" ;
tauice:missing_value = -32767s ;
tauice:_FillValue = -32767s ;
tauice:standard_name = "downward_y_stress_at_sea_ice_bas" ;
tauice:add_offset = 0.f ;
tauice:scale_factor = 6.104447e-05f ;
tauice:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
tauice:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
tauice:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short qtot(x, y, x) ;
qtot:long_name = "Net heat flux into ocean" ;
qtot:units = "w m-2" ;
qtot:missing_value = -32767s ;
qtot:_FillValue = -32767s ;
qtot:standard_name = "surface_downward_heat_flux_in_sea_water" ;
qtot:add_offset = 0.f ;
qtot:scale_factor = 0.0915667f ;
qtot:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
qtot:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
qtot:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short qtotair(x, y, x) ;
qtotair:long_name = "Net surface atmospheric heat flux" ;
qtotair:units = "w m-2" ;
qtotair:missing_value = -32767s ;
qtotair:_FillValue = -32767s ;
qtotair:standard_name = "surface_downward_heat_flux_in_air" ;
qtotair:add_offset = 0.f ;
qtotair:scale_factor = 0.0915667f ;
qtotair:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
qtotair:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
qtotair:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short qsw(x, y, x) ;

```

```

qsw:long_name = "Net surface shortwave heat flux" ;
qsw:units = "w m-2" ;
qsw:missing_value = -32767s ;
qsw:_FillValue = -32767s ;
qsw:standard_name = "net_downward_shortwave_flux_in_air" ;
qsw:add_offset = 1000.f ;
qsw:scale_factor = 0.03052223f ;
qsw:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
qsw:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
qsw:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short fwflux(y, x) ;
fwflux:long_name = "Freshwater flux into ocean" ;
fwflux:units = "kg m-2 s-1" ;
fwflux:missing_value = -32767s ;
fwflux:_FillValue = -32767s ;
fwflux:standard_name = "water_flux_into_ocean" ;
fwflux:add_offset = 0.f ;
fwflux:scale_factor = 3.052224e-08f ;
fwflux:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
fwflux:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
fwflux:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short fice(y, x) ;
fice:long_name = "Sea Ice Concentration" ;
fice:units = "" ;
fice:missing_value = -32767s ;
fice:_FillValue = -32767s ;
fice:standard_name = "sea_ice_area_fraction" ;
fice:add_offset = 0.5f ;
fice:scale_factor = 1.556634e-05f ;
fice:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
fice:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
fice:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short hice(y, x) ;
hice:long_name = "Sea Ice Thickness (area average)" ;
hice:units = "m" ;
hice:missing_value = -32767s ;
hice:_FillValue = -32767s ;
hice:standard_name = "sea_ice_thickness" ;
hice:add_offset = 7.495f ;
hice:scale_factor = 0.0002290694f ;
hice:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
hice:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
hice:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short hsnow(y, x) ;
hsnow:long_name = "Thickness of snow on top of sea ice (area average)" ;
hsnow:units = "m" ;
hsnow:missing_value = -32767s ;
hsnow:_FillValue = -32767s ;
hsnow:standard_name = "surface_snow_thickness" ;
hsnow:add_offset = 7.495f ;
hsnow:scale_factor = 0.0002290694f ;
hsnow:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
hsnow:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
hsnow:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short uice(y, x) ;
uice:long_name = "X velocity component of sea ice (area average)" ;
uice:units = "m s-1" ;
uice:missing_value = -32767s ;
uice:_FillValue = -32767s ;
uice:standard_name = "x_sea_ice_velocity" ;
uice:add_offset = 0.f ;
uice:scale_factor = 6.104447e-05f ;
uice:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
uice:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
uice:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short vice(y, x) ;
vice:long_name = "Y velocity component of sea ice (area average)" ;
vice:units = "m s-1" ;
vice:missing_value = -32767s ;
vice:_FillValue = -32767s ;
vice:standard_name = "y_sea_ice_velocity" ;
vice:add_offset = 0.f ;
vice:scale_factor = 6.104447e-05f ;

```

```
vice:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
vice:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
vice:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;
short htndncy(y, x) ;
vice:long_name = "Sea ice growth due to thermodynamics (area average)" ;
vice:units = "m s-1" ;
vice:missing_value = -32767s ;
vice:_FillValue = -32767s ;
vice:standard_name = "tendency_of_sea_ice_thickness_due_to_thermodynamics" ;
vice:add_offset = 0.f ;
vice:scale_factor = 6.104447e-05f ;
vice:grid_mapping = "polar_stereographic" ;
vice:coordinates = "longitude latitude" ;
vice:cell_methods = "lat: lon: time: mean" ;

// global attributes:
:title = "TOPAZ model results" ;
:comment = "Daily Averaged fields" ;
:institution = "NERSC, Thormoeh lens gate 47, N-5006 Bergen, Norway" ;
:history = "20051014:Created by program hyc2proj, version V0.1" ;
:source = "NERSC-HYCOM model fields" ;
:references = "http://topaz.nersc.no http://www.mersea.eu.org" ;
:field_type = "Daily average fields" ;
:Conventions = "CF-1.0" ;
:field_date = "0000-01-01" ;
:bulletin_date = "0000-01-01" ;
}
```

Class 2 data

Class 2 products are model output along high-resolution sections and moorings. There is no repeat section of observations in the Arctic to our knowledge.

9. Fields to be produced along sections

- **2D daily fields (s, z) along sections** T, S, U and V
sampled every 10 km exact locations given in document [REF9].
- **1D daily fields (s) along sections** Fice, Hice, Uice, Vice
sampled every 10 km: exact locations given in document [REF9]

Figure 2: Arctic sections indicated in blue. Left, sections proposed for sea-ice. Right, extension of sections in the global metrics design (see also [REF9]). Sections are described in Table 9.

10. Position of sections

The ice-free sections common to the NAT and ARCTIC areas are not repeated here, the Class 2 and Class 3 metrics are defined in [REF9].

Sections	Lon 1	Lat 1	Lon 2	Lat 2	Transport	Classes	Parameter Name
(1) Fram Strait	-20.	79.	15.	79.	Yes	S < 34.9 psu S > 34.9 psu	T1=t _{1p1} T2=t _{1m1} T3=t ₁₂ T4=t _{m2}
(2) Denmark Strait	-37.	66.1	-22.68	66.	Yes	$\sigma_0 < 27.8$ $27.8 < \sigma_0$	T5 to T8=t _{2p1} , t _{2m1} t _{2p2} , t _{2m2}
(3) Lancaster Sound	-82	73.4	-82	74.9	Yes	No classes	T9= t _{3p} T10= t _{3m}
(4) Jones Strait	-80.5	75.2	-80.1	76.6	Yes	No classes	T11= t _{4p} T12= t _{4m}
(5) Robeson Channel	-77.	78.1	-71	78	Yes	No classes	T13= t _{5p} T14= t _{5m}
(6) Hudson Strait	-64.7	60.4	-65	61.5	Yes	No classes	T15= t _{6p} T16= t _{6m}
(7) Bear Island	20.9	71.5	16	77	Yes	S<34.9 psu S>34.9 psu	T17 to T20=t _{7p1} , t _{7m1} t _{7p2} , t _{7m2}
(8) Kola Section	33.5	69.5	33.5	74	Yes	S<34.9 psu S>34.9 psu	T21 to T24=t _{p1} , t _{m1} t _{p2} , t _{m2}
(9) Spitzberg Franz J. Land	26.8	80.2	58.4	81.9	Yes	No classes	T25= t _{9p} T26= t _{9m}
(10) Franz J. Land Nov. Zemlija	58.4	79.9	65.9	76.6	Yes	$\sigma_0 < 27.8$ $\sigma_0 > 27.8$ or S > 34.6	T27 to T30= t _{10p1} , t _{10m1} t _{10p2} , t _{10m2}
(11) Kara Gate	57.8	70.5	58.3	70.4	Yes	No classes	T31= t _{11p} T32= t _{11m}
(12) Bering Strait	-171	66	-166	66	Yes	No classes	T33= t _{12p} T34= t _{12m}
(13) Arctic 0	0	90	0	70	No	No classes	T35= t _{13p} T36= t _{13m}
(14) Arctic 30	30	90	30	70	No	“	T37= t _{14p} T38= t _{14m}
(15) Arctic 60	60	90	60	70	No	“	T39= t _{15p} T40= t _{15m}
(16) Arctic 90	90	90	90	70	No	“	T41= t _{16p} T42= t _{16m}
(17) Arctic 120	120	90	120	70	No	“	T43= t _{17p} T44= t _{17m}
(18) Arctic 150	150	90	150	70	No	“	T45= t _{18p} T46= t _{18m}
(19) Arctic 180	180	90	180	66	No	“	T47= t _{19p} T48= t _{19m}

(20) Arctic -150	-150	90	-150	70	No	“	T49= t20 _p T50= t20 _m
(21) Arctic -120	-120	90	-120	68	No	“	T51= t21 _p T52= t21 _m
(22) Arctic -90	-90	90	-90	55	No	“	T53= t22 _p T54= t22 _m
(23) Arctic -60	-60	90	-60	55	No	“	T55= t23 _p T56= t23 _m
(24) Arctic -30	-30	90	-30	80	No	“	T57= t24 _p T58= t24 _m

Table 9: Class 2 and 3 Arctic sections. *p/m* stands respectively for positive and negative parameter name.

(2) Some of these sections may be already present in other TEP standard products (Denmark Strait). The reasons for this redundancy is that these sections are seasonally ice covered and ice parameters are only stored in ARCTIC files. The density sill for Class 3 data is repeated from MERSEA Strand 1 [REF3], although the Class 3 results can already be deduced from the NAT sections and may be considered as redundant. Transports from 1999 to 2003 are in Marcrander *et al.* (2005) *Geoph. Res. Let.*, Vol 32, L06606.

(7) Bear Island section crosses Bear Island (19.1E, 74.3N), 34.9 psu represents N. Atl. Water. (Ingvaldsen et al. 2004, *Continental Shelf Res.* 24, pp. 1015-1032)

(10) Midtun (1985) *Deep Sea Res.* Vol 32, 10, pp. 1233 – 1241. 34.6 psu or 27.8 represent intermediate water. 34.95 psu for bottom water.

(11) (12) Only coastal water in Bering Sea and Kara Gate.

11. Position of moorings

Available moorings providing data in 2006 have been identified in the Arctic region (Figure 3), and described in Table 10.

Figure 3: Position of moorings operating in the Arctic in 2006.

To compare forecasting systems in the Arctic with observations from these moorings, identical physical variables deduced from the model outputs should be stored as along sections, thus 1D and 0D (time series) fields.

Moorin g	UL S	Latitud e	Longitud e	Description	Originator
ARC1	No	71 46'N	131 53'W	CABOS*	IARC, UAF + IOS, Canada
ARC2	No	79 56'N	142 21'E	NABOS*	IARC, UAF + Laval Univ. Canada
ARC3	No	76 44'N	125 55'E	NABOS*	IARC, UAF + AWI Germany
ARC4	No	78 28'N	125 40'E	NABOS	IARC, UAF
ARC5	No	80 58'N	105 00'E	NABOS	IARC, Univ. of Alaska
ARC6	No	80 22'N	101 26'E	NABOS*	IARC, UAF + AWI Germany

ARC7	Yes	90	0	NPEO	APL, Univ. of Washington
ARC8	No	81 34'N	30 55'E	NABOS*	IARC, UAF + NPI, Norway
ARC9	No	66	2	Station MIKE (Norwegian Sea)	Met.no, Univ. in Bergen

Table 10: Position of Arctic moorings. *: observations can be provided upon justified request. ULS: Upward Looking Sonar.

12. Example

The vector rotation has not been applied here for user friendliness. Velocities are Northwards and Eastwards. For file description see also Table 14.

```
netcdf topaz_V1_mersea_arctic_dc_class2_section001_b20040630_f200406279999 {
dimensions:
  track = 29 ;
  depth = 33 ;
variables:
  float longitude(track) ;
    longitude:long_name = "longitude" ;
    longitude:units = "degrees_east" ;
    longitude:valid_range = -180., 180. ;
    longitude:missing_value = -1000000000. ;
    longitude:standard_name = "longitude" ;
  float latitude(track) ;
    latitude:long_name = "latitude" ;
    latitude:units = "degrees_north" ;
    latitude:valid_range = -90., 90. ;
    latitude:missing_value = -1000000000. ;
    latitude:standard_name = "latitude" ;
  float track(track) ;
    track:long_name = "Distance Along Section" ;
    track:units = "kilometer" ;
    track:valid_range = 0., 20000. ;
    track:missing_value = -1000000000. ;
    track:axis = "X" ;
  float depth(depth) ;
    depth:long_name = "Z levels" ;
    depth:units = "m" ;
    depth:valid_range = 0., 5501. ;
    depth:missing_value = -1000000000. ;
    depth:standard_name = "depth" ;
    depth:positive = "down" ;
    depth:axis = "Y" ;
  short temperature(depth, track) ;
    temperature:long_name = "Potential Temperature" ;
    temperature:units = "degree_Celsius" ;
    temperature:missing_value = -32767s ;
    temperature:_FillValue = -32767s ;
    temperature:standard_name = "sea_water_potential_temperature" ;
    temperature:add_offset = 21.5 ;
    temperature:scale_factor = 0.00071727253304032 ;
  short salinity(depth, track) ;
    salinity:long_name = "Salinity" ;
    salinity:units = "ppt" ;
    salinity:missing_value = -32767s ;
    salinity:_FillValue = -32767s ;
    salinity:standard_name = "sea_water_salinity" ;
    salinity:add_offset = 26.5 ;
    salinity:scale_factor = 0.00050361688490065 ;
  short u(depth, track) ;
    u:long_name = "Eastward velocity" ;
```

```

u:units = "meter second-1" ;
u:missing_value = -32767s ;
u:_FillValue = -32767s ;
u:standard_name = "eastward_sea_water_velocity" ;
u:add_offset = 0. ;
u:scale_factor = 0.000152611177242621 ;
short v(depth, track) ;
v:long_name = "Northward velocity" ;
v:units = "meter second-1" ;
v:_FillValue = -32767s ;
v:missing_value = -32767s ;
v:standard_name = "northward_sea_water_velocity" ;
v:add_offset = 0. ;
v:scale_factor = 0.000152611177242621 ;
short uice(track) ;
u:long_name = "Eastward sea ice velocity" ;
u:units = "meter second-1" ;
u:missing_value = -32767s ;
u:_FillValue = -32767s ;
u:standard_name = "eastward_sea_ice_velocity" ;
u:add_offset = 0. ;
u:scale_factor = 0.000152611177242621 ;
short vice(track) ;
v:long_name = "Northward sea ice velocity" ;
v:units = "meter second-1" ;
v:_FillValue = -32767s ;
v:missing_value = -32767s ;
v:standard_name = "northward_sea_ice_velocity" ;
v:add_offset = 0. ;
v:scale_factor = 0.000152611177242621 ;

// global attributes:
:title = "TOPAZ Daily average -- MERSEA NORMAL Sections" ;
:section_name = " FRAM STRAIT" ;
:institution = "NERSC, Thormoelensgate 47, Bergen, Norway" ;
:Dataset_generation_date = "20050706" ;
:Conventions = "COARDS" ;
:history = "Created 20040706 by program daily2sectionnc V0.1" ;
:references = "http://www.mersea.eu.org , http://topaz.nersc.no" ;
:field_type = "Daily average fields" ;
:field_date = "2005-06-27" ;
:bulletin_date = "2005-06-30" ;
:bulletin_type = "Hindcast" ;

```

Class 3 data

The following quantities will be computed as Class 3 diagnostics from the native model grid: (first two are taken from MERSEA Strand 1 [REF3 and REF4] and amended wrt orientation of transport through section). Class 3 file description is provided at Table 15.

- **Daily estimates of transports through specific sections** T^+ , T^-

See the identification of these sections in Table 9

The T^+ and T^- transports are defined as daily estimates and calculated by:

$$T^+ = \int_{l_2}^{l_1} dl \int_{-z_b}^{\eta} u^+_n dz$$

$$T^- = \int_{l_2}^{l_1} dl \int_{-z_b}^{\eta} u^-_n dz$$

where l_1, l_2 are the extremes of the section, u_n^+ and u_n^- are the velocity components normal to the section in the positive and negative direction, η is the free surface and z_b is the bottom depth. Positive direction is taken to the north for the non-meridional sections and to the east for the meridional sections.

u_n^+ and u_n^- are defined as

$$u_n^+(z) = \delta(+1) u_n(z) \quad \text{with } \delta(+1)=1 \quad \text{if } u_n(z) > 0 \quad \text{and } \delta(+1)=0 \quad \text{if } u_n(z) < 0$$

$$u_n^-(z) = \delta(+1) u_n(z) \quad \text{with } \delta(+1)=1 \quad \text{if } u_n(z) < 0 \quad \text{and } \delta(+1)=0 \quad \text{if } u_n(z) > 0$$

Note: Please use as a convention “**positive flow to the right hand side of the section when looking from the start to the end of the section**” (in more mathematical words, the positive direction is $\vec{k} \times \vec{s}$ the vector product of the depths axes unit vector times the section axis unit vector, the depths axis being oriented downwards).

- **Daily estimates of transports through sections in density, temperature or salinity classes** $\text{Tr}_i^+, \text{Tr}_i^-$
See the identification of these sections in Table 2 with $r=\Delta\rho, \Delta\theta$ or ΔS

These transports are defined as a daily estimate and calculated by:

$$T^{+/-} = \int_{l_2}^{l_1} dl \int_{z_{p1}}^{z_{p2}} u^{+/-}_n dz$$

- where l_1, l_2 are the extremes of the section, u_n is the velocity component normal to the section in the positive and negative direction, z_{p1} and z_{p2} are the depths bounding the density, temperature or salinity classes considered. T^+ and T^- are defined as above.
- **Daily estimates of ice area and ice volume transport, through specific sections** $\text{IAT}^+, \text{IAT}^-, \text{IVT}^+, \text{IVT}^-$
See the identification of these sections in Table 2

These transports are defined as a daily estimate and calculated by:

$$\text{IAT}^{+/-} = \int_{l_2}^{l_1} f_{ice} \times u_{ice}^{+/-}_n dl$$

$$\text{IVT}^{+/-} = \int_{l_2}^{l_1} f_{ice} \times h_{ice} \times u_{ice}^{+/-}_n dl$$

where l_1, l_2 are the extremes of the section, $u_{ice}^{+/-}_n$ is the ice drift component normal to the section in the positive and negative direction (convention defined above), f_{ice} and h_{ice} are the ice concentration and thickness.

- **Total ice extent, concentration averaged.**

The ice extent is a daily estimate based on a 15% threshold on ice concentration per grid cell:

$$IE = \int_{y1.x1}^{y2.x2} \delta_{f_{ice}>15\%} dx dy$$

- **Total ice area, concentration averaged**

The ice area is a daily estimate and defined as

$$IA = \int_{y1.x1}^{y2.x2} f_{ice} dx dy$$

- **Total ice volume**

The ice volume is a daily estimate and defined as

$$IV = \int_{y1.x1}^{y2.x2} f_{ice} \times h_{ice} dx dy$$

- **Total area of leads**

The area of leads is a daily estimate and defined as

$$LA = \int_{y1.x1}^{y2.x2} (1 - f_{ice}) \times \delta_{f_{ice}>15\%} dx dy$$

- **Heat fluxes through leads**

The heat fluxes through leads is a daily estimate and defined as

$$LQ = \int_{y1.x1}^{y2.x2} F_w \times (1 - f_{ice}) \times \delta_{f_{ice}>15\%} dx dy ,$$

F_w being the downward heat flux in water (leads) and the Kronecker symbol discarding all grid cells with less than 15% ice covered, so that fluxes in open water are not included.

Class 4 data

13. Available observation dataset

This is a primary list of observations to measure performance against. They should be assembled on a common location for coherence of the comparisons. For many of the in-situ data, the timeliness issue should be addressed. Note also that a common policy has been adopted for comparison against T/S in-situ data, described in [REF8].

- **SSM/I ice concentrations** are available daily in near real-time (3 days delay): they are assimilated in TOPAZ and FOAM (Arctic and NEA TEP), but the products are based on different algorithms. The differences are likely small, so OSI/SAF products can be used. saf.met.no
- **Ice drift:** Cersat/Ifremer products by R. Ezraty (only data source available accessed by all participants) data from QuickSCAT (60km resolution) or AMSR (30km resolution), data are 2-, 3-, or 6-days drift. www.ifremer.fr/cersat. Advised data are merged 60 km resolution 3-days drift (R. Ezraty, personal communication).

- **Moorings** from the NPEO, NABOS and CABOS as in Table 10 (temperature, salinity and currents), hundreds of stations in the Barents Sea from Norwegian IMR (temperature, salinity) but with low sampling frequency. Data made available to research within one year from acquisition, <http://nabos.iarc.uaf.edu/> <http://psc.apl.washington.edu/northpole/>
- Fram Strait **Moorings are equipped with ULS** (Upward Looking Sonar) and measure ice thickness. TOP1 data will not be made available before 2007. <http://asof.npolar.no/>
- **Ice-drifting buoys** (IABP) from NSIDC, both real-time observations and quality-controlled delayed-mode observations. <http://iabp.apl.washington.edu/>
- **Sea-going expeditions:**
 - Aerial NPEO CTD casts every year in April, data expected end of 2006. <http://psc.apl.washington.edu/northpole/Data.html>
 - NABOS 2005 cruise (I/B Kapitan Danitsyn) 12/09/2005 to 22/05/2005, data expected end of 2006.
 - AWI Polarstern expeditions. Icebreakers sections are scheduled for the IPY (Intl. Polar Year) 2007-2008 (TOP2 / last year of MERSEA).
 - IMR standard sections (Kola section, Bear Island Section)
- **Tide gauges** from GLOSS and ESEAS. <http://ilikai.soest.hawaii.edu/uhs/c/data.html>.

14. Class 4 diagnostics

As presented in [REF8], for TOP1, performance of the forecasting systems is assessed on the “observational space”, and not on the “model space”. It means that diagnostics are based on “model-to-obs” differences analysis and statistics.

The forecasting system outputs that are considered are:

- Hind cast or nowcast.
- Analysis.
- Forecast, at typical forecast time of 3 and 6-day ahead
- Persistence, corresponding to a given forecast time

Climatologies (to be defined for each variable) are also used to establish the forecasting skills.

The forecasting skills are based on a two-stages procedure:

- First the binning of the “model-to-obs” differences following the appropriate method. Horizontal, vertical and time scales should be defined according: to number of data, consistency of physical phenomena, geographical considerations.....
- Second, “tools” have to be selected to evaluate the forecasting skills, based on statistics: e.g., RMS, correlation..... or peak detection rules, or other considerations.

Class 4 files have also to be defined (Table 16), in order to be compliant with OpenDap rules.

SUMMARY table

The following tables are adapted from [REF2]

Class 1 daily products primary gridded	a file per configuration model, per area, per parameter or per class , per day <i>[model_[config_version]_[target_area_grid]_[parameter]_[bulletin_date]_[field_date].nc</i> For example:
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<p>products:</p> <p>T</p> <p>S</p> <p>U</p> <p>V</p> <p>(regular 3-d grid)</p> <p>τwind</p> <p>totnetHF,</p> <p>shortwHF</p> <p>E-P-R</p> <p>SSH</p> <p>BarSTRMF</p> <p>MLD</p> <p>Fice</p> <p>Hice</p> <p>Uice</p> <p>Vice</p> <p>Hsnow</p> <p>Htendency</p> <p>τice</p> <p>(2D grid)</p>	<p>MERCATOR_PSY2VI_MERSEA_ARCTIC_grid1o8_da_pppp_byyyymmdd_fyyymmddhhmm.nc</p> <p>where</p> <p>grid1o8= 1/8° regular grid</p> <p>da= d for depth with respect to the various predefined depth levels a= the 12 MERSEA depth levels for ARCTIC</p> <p>ARCTIC ARCTIC area</p> <p>pppp =the parameter short name if only one parameter per file =the class short name if all parameters of a class in one file</p> <p>b for bulletin date, = To that is the date the operational system creates its ocean bulletin (NB: an ocean bulletin is dated To and can covered, for instance [To-7 ...To ... To+7])</p> <p>yyymmdd= for management issues (releases) on the ocean bulletin y for year, m for month, d for day</p> <p>f for field date of the best estimate, = To \pm i (i for daily occurrence)</p> <p>yyymmddhhmm= for management issues (releases) on the ocean bulletin y for year, m for month, d for day, h for hour, m for minute</p> <p><i>Note 1 : They are two type of files, 'average' values (on a day) – preferred one - or 'snapshot' values (e.g. at 12 am). For the first case, we will have yyymmdd9999, for the second case, yyymmdd1200.</i></p> <p><i>Note 2 : to know if the data are hindcast, analysis of the day or forecast, just compare field_date to bulletin_date</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - if field date < bulletin date it is an hindcast, - if field date = bulletin date it is the analysis of the day - if field date > bulletin date it is a forecast,
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Table 11: Class 1 daily files description.

<p>Class 1 monthly external products</p> <p>T S (regular 3-d grid)</p>	<p>a file per climatology data base, per area, per parameter or per class , per month</p> <p><i>[climatology_[config_version]_[target_area_grid]_[parameter]_[field_date].nc</i></p> <p>For example:</p> <p><i>LEVITUS_V1982_MERSEA_ARCTIC_grid1o8_da_pppp_fyyyymmdd.nc</i></p> <p>where</p> <p>grid1o8= 1/8° regular grid</p> <p>da= d for depth with respect to the various predefined depth levels a= the 12 MERSEA depth levels for ARCTIC</p> <p>ARCTIC Arctic area</p> <p>ppp =the parameter short name if only one parameter per file =the class short name if all parameters of a class in one file</p> <p>f for field date of the climatology,</p> <p>yyyymmdd= for management issues (releases) on the ocean bulletin y for year, m for month, d for day</p>
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Table 12: Class 1 monthly averages file description.

<p>Class 1 external products 2D bottom bathymetry</p>	<p>a file per model configuration, per area, per parameter</p> <p><i>[model_[config_version]_[target_area_grid]_[parameter].nc</i></p> <p>For example:</p> <p><i>MERCATOR_PSY2V1_MERSEA_ARCTIC_grid1o8_pppp.nc</i></p> <p>where</p> <p>grid1o8= 1/8° regular grid</p> <p>ARCTIC Arctic area</p> <p>ppp =the parameter short name</p>
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Table 13: Example of Class 1 external files

<p>Class 2 products</p> <p>Primary gridded products:</p> <p>T S U V</p> <p>Fice Hice Uice Vice</p> <p>higher resolution on vertical sections (no XBT section in Arctic) or at moorings</p>	<p>Daily a file per configuration model, per section, per parameter or per class , per day</p> <p><i>[model_[conf_version]_[target_area_section_grid]_[parameter]_[bulletin_date]_[field_date].nc</i></p> <p>For example:</p> <p><i>MERCATOR_PSY2V1_MERSEA_ARCTIC_section2_dc_pppp_byyyymmdd_fyyymmddhhmm.nc</i></p> <p>where</p> <p>section2= Denmark Strait (cf. Table 9)</p> <p>dc= d for depth with respect to the various predefined depth levels c= the 33 LEVITUS depth levels d= the 72 Reynaud depth levels etc...</p> <p>ARCTIC Arctic area</p> <p>ppp =the parameter short name if only one parameter per file =the class short name if all parameters of a class in one file</p> <p>b for bulletin date, = To that is the date the operational system creates its ocean bulletin (NB: an ocean bulletin is dated To and can covered, for instance [To-7 ...To ... To+7])</p> <p>yyymmdd= for management issues (releases) on the ocean bulletin y for year, m for month, d for day</p> <p>f for field date of the best estimate, = To ± i (i for daily occurrence)</p> <p>yyymmddhhmm= for management issues (releases) on the ocean bulletin y for year, m for month, d for day, h for hour, m for minute</p> <p><i>Note 1 : They are two type of files, ‘average’ values (on a day) – preferred one - or ‘snapshot’ values (e.g. at 12 am). For the first case, we will have yyymmdd9999, for the second case, yyymmdd1200.</i></p> <p><i>Note 2 : to know if the data are hindcast, analysis of the day or forecast, just compare field_date to bulletin_date - if field date < bulletin date it is an hindcast, - if field date = bulletin date it is the analysis of the day - if field date > bulletin date it is a forecast,</i></p>
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Table 14: Class 2 files description.

<p>Class 3 products Transports through sections: T1 to T58, IAT1 to IAT22 IVT1 to IVT22 for ARCTIC</p> <p>Integrated values IE, IA, IV, LA, LQ</p>	<p>Daily best estimates a file per configuration model, per area, per parameter or per class , per day</p> <p><i>[model_[config_version]_[target_area]_[parameter]_[bulletin_date]_[field_date].nc</i></p> <p>For example: <i>MERCATOR_PSY2VI_MERSEA_ARCTIC_pppp_byyyymmdd_fyyymmddhhmm.nc</i></p> <p>where</p> <p>ARCTIC Arctic area</p> <p>ppp = transport T1 to T58 + IE + IA+ IV + LA + LQ for ARCTIC</p> <p>b for bulletin date, = To that is the date the operational system creates its ocean bulletin (NB: an ocean bulletin is dated To and can covered, for instance [To-7 ...To ... To+7])</p> <p>yyymmdd= for management issues (releases) on the ocean bulletin y for year, m for month, d for day, h for hour, m for minut, s for second</p> <p>f for field date of the best estimate, = To ± i (i for daily occurrence)</p> <p>yyymmddhhmm= for management issues (releases) on the ocean bulletin y for year, m for month, d for day, h for hour, m for minute</p>
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Table 15: Class 3 files description.

<p>Class 4 products Performance evaluation parameters</p>	<p>Weekly updates, interpolated to observation space, one daily average for each forecast horizon day TBD</p>
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Table 16: Class 4 files description.